

A Montague-Style Denotational Semantics for the Direct Interpretation of Natural Language Queries to Triple Stores and Databases

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Abstract—Many Natural Language (NL) Query Interfaces to data stores convert queries to a formal query language and then execute the formal query in order to obtain the result. This is problematic when handling chained prepositional phrases. An alternative approach is to treat the NL query language as a formal language and to execute the NL query directly with respect to the data store. This approach can accommodate a wide range of NL queries and is relatively easy to implement if it is based on an extension of Richard Montague’s denotational semantics (MS) for natural language. The higher-order functional capability of the programming language Haskell facilitates both the implementation of MS and the close integration of syntactic analysis with semantic processing. A publicly accessible web-based NL interface to a remote Semantic Web data store has been constructed to demonstrate the viability of this approach. The approach can be directly adapted for use with relational databases.

Keywords—Natural language processing, natural language semantics, semantic web, Montague Semantics.

I. INTRODUCTION

MANY Natural Language Query Interfaces to relational databases and semantic web triplestores convert the NL query to a formal query language such as SQL or SPARQL and then execute the formal query with respect to the relational database or semantic web triplestore respectively. One problem with these approaches is that the interface is restricted by the difficulty of translating complex NL phrases to the formal query language. In particular, queries with chained prepositional phrases containing quantifiers have been difficult to accommodate. Examples of such queries are: “who discovered two moons with a telescope in 1877 at us_naval_observatory”, and “where was a telescope used by hall to discover phobos”

An alternative approach is to treat the NL query as an expression of the lambda calculus, using an extended form of the denotational semantics of Richard Montague [1], and to calculate the answer directly by interpreting the lambda calculus expression with respect to the data store. All that are required to be extracted from the data store are unary relations corresponding to sets of entities associated with the denotations of common nouns, adjectives and intransitive verbs, and the $n^2 - n$ binary relations associated with n -ary transitive verbs.

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Montague semantics can be easily implemented in a pure functional programming language such as Haskell. The higher-order functional capability of Haskell and the ability to partially apply higher-order functions enable Montague denotations of words such as “every” to be directly defined in the language. Furthermore, the availability of parser combinator libraries enables the construction of Executable Attribute Grammars (EAGs) within the language. This lends itself to a direct implementation of Montague-style integration of syntax rules with semantic rules.

II. A PROTOTYPE SYSTEM

The pure functional programming language Haskell was used to build a prototype NL interface to a semantic web triplestore [2].

Some example queries that are supported by the interface include:

- did hall discover every moon that orbits mars
- how many moons were discovered by hall and kuiper
- how many moons were discovered by hall or kuiper
- every moon was discovered by a person
- which planets are orbited by a moon that was discovered by galileo
- hall discovered a moon that orbits mars
- which moons that orbit mars were discovered by hall
- every moon orbits every planet
- every planet is orbited by a moon
- a planet is orbited by a moon
- does phobos orbit mars
- which moon was discovered by a person
- who discovered a moon with a telescope
- what was discovered in 1877 in us_naval_observatory
- how many things were discovered in us_naval_observatory
- which planets are orbited by two moons that were discovered with a telescope
- what moon was discovered by one person in 1877
- one planet is orbited by two moons
- which vacuumous moon that orbits jupiter was discovered by nicholson or hall with a telescope in 1938 in mt_wilson or mt_hopkins
- what planet is orbited by a moon that was discovered in 1684
- what moon that orbits jupiter was discovered in 1951 by a person in mt_wilson

- how many moons were discovered in 1938 by a person with a telescope
- what was used to discover phobos
- what did someone use to discover a moon
- how did someone discover a moon
- where was a telescope used to discover a moon at us_naval_observatory

If a syntactically ambiguous query is entered, the results from each possible interpretation are returned separated by semicolon characters.

III. RELATED WORK

Orakel [3] is a portable NLQI which uses a Montague-like grammar and a lambda-calculus semantics to analyze queries. The approach described in this paper is similar to Orakel in this respect. However, in Orakel, queries are translated to an expression of first-order logic enriched with predicates for query and numerical operators. These expressions are translated to SPARQL or F-Logic. Orakel supports negation, limited quantification, and simple prepositional phrases. Portability is achieved by having the lexicon customized by people with limited linguistic expertise. It is claimed that Orakel can accommodate n -ary relations with $n \geq 2$. However, no examples are given of such queries being translated to SPARQL.

YAGO2 [4] is a semantic knowledge base containing reified triples extracted from Wikipedia, WordNet and GeoNames, representing nearly 0.5 billion facts. Reification is achieved by tagging each triple with an identifier. However, this is hidden from the user who views the knowledge base as a set of "SPOTL" quintuples, where T is for time and L for location. The SPOTLX query language is used to access YAGO2. Although SPOTLX is a formal language, it is significantly easier to use than is SPARQL for queries involving time and location (which in SPARQL would require many joins for reified triplestores). SPOTLX does not accommodate quantification or negation, but can handle queries with prepositional aspects involving time and location. However, no mention is made of chained complex PPs.

Alexandria [5] is an event-based triplestore, with 160 million triples (representing 13 million n -ary relationships), derived from FreeBase. Alexandria uses a neo-Davidsonian [6] event-based semantics. In Alexandria, queries are parsed to a syntactic dependency graph, mapped to a semantic description, and translated to SPARQL queries containing named graphs. Queries with simple PPs are accommodated. However, no mention is made of negation, nested quantification, or chained complex PPs.

The systems referred to above have made substantial progress in handling ambiguity and matching NL query words to URIs. However, they appear to have hit a roadblock with respect to natural-language coverage. Most can handle simple PPs such as in "who was born in 1918" but none can handle chained complex PPs, containing quantifiers, such as "in us_naval_observatory in 1877 or 1860". There appear to be three reasons for this: 1) those NLQIs that were designed for

non-reified triplestores, such as DBpedia, do not appear to be easily extended to reified triplestores that are necessary for complex PPs. 2) those NLQIs that were designed for non-reified or reified triplestores, and which translate the NL queries to SPARQL, suffer from the fact that SPARQL was originally designed for non-reified triplestores. Although SPARQL was extended to handle "named graphs" [7] which support a limited form of reification but appear to be suitable only for provenance data. SPARQL was also extended to accommodate triple identifiers. 3) The YAGO2 system is the only system that has an NLQI for a reified triplestore that does not translate to SPARQL. However, YAGO2 can only accommodate PPs related to time and location and does not support quantification.

Reference [8] implemented lambda calculus with respect to natural language, in Prolog, and [9] have extensively discussed such implementation in Haskell. Implementation of the lambda calculus for open-domain question answering has been investigated by [10]. The SQUALL query language [11], [12] is a controlled natural language (CNL) for querying and updating triplestores represented as RDF graphs. SQUALL can return answers directly from remote triplestores, as the approach described in this paper does, using simple SPARQL-endpoint triple retrieval commands. It can also be translated to SPARQL queries which can be processed by SPARQL endpoints for faster computation of answers. SQUALL syntax and semantics are defined as a Montague Grammar facilitating the translation to SPARQL. SQUALL can handle quantification, aggregation, some forms of negation, and chained complex prepositional phrases. It is also written in a functional language. However, some queries in SQUALL require the use of variables and low-level relational algebraic operators (see for example, the queries on page 118 of [12]).

IV. THE EXTENSION TO MONTAGUE SEMANTICS

MS [1] defines the meaning of words, phrases, sentences and queries in terms of a space of functions that is built over a set of entities (the universe of discourse) and the Boolean values *True* and *False*. For example, the word "moon" denotes the characteristic function (logical predicate) which maps entities to *True* or *False*. The result is *True* if the entity is a moon, and *False* otherwise. One of Montague's many insights was his recognition that proper nouns such as "Phobos" do not denote entities; rather they denote functions that take characteristic functions as argument and return Boolean values as result. For example "Phobos" denotes the function $\lambda f f e_{phobos}$ where e_{phobos} represents the entity associated with the name Phobos. For readers not familiar with the Lambda Calculus, the expression $\lambda f expr$ is the name (and definition) of a function which, when applied to an argument g returns as result the expression $expr$ with all instances of f in $expr$ replaced by g . According to MS, the phrase "Phobos spins" is interpreted as shown below, where $a \implies b$ indicates that b is the result of evaluating a , $\|a\|$ represents the denotation (meaning) of a , w_pred is the logical

predicate associated with the word w , and λ is the Lambda symbol.

$$\begin{aligned} & \|phobos spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & \|phobos\| \|spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & \lambda f f e_{phobos} \|spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & \lambda f f e_{phobos} spins_pred \\ \Rightarrow & spins_pred e_{phobos} \\ \Rightarrow & True \end{aligned}$$

owing to the fact that Phobos does spin.

Montague's treatment of quantifiers such as "a", "every", "some", "one" etc. is to treat their denotations as higher-order functions. For example, the word "every" denotes the following function:

$$\begin{aligned} \|every\| &= \lambda p \lambda q \forall x (p x \Rightarrow q x) \\ \|a\| &= \lambda p \lambda q (\exists x) (p x \wedge q x) \end{aligned}$$

For example:

$$\begin{aligned} & \|every moon spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & (\|every moon\|) \|spins\| \quad (\text{from syntactic parsing}) \\ \Rightarrow & (\lambda p \lambda q \forall x (p x \Rightarrow q x) moon_pred) spins_pred \\ \Rightarrow & (\lambda q \forall x (moon_pred x \Rightarrow q x)) spins_pred \\ \Rightarrow & \forall x moon_pred x \Rightarrow spins_pred x \\ \Rightarrow & True \quad (\text{every moon in} \\ & \quad \text{the universe of discourse spins}) \end{aligned}$$

A. A Computationally Tractable Version of Montague Semantics

The direct implementation of MS is not practical for applications with a large universe of discourse owing to the use of characteristic functions. For example, the denotation of "every" given above is computationally intractable in a query such as "does every moon spin" as it would require the characteristic function that is the denotation of "moon" to be applied to every entity in the universe of discourse. A more efficient alternative approach is to use the sets defined by characteristic functions directly in denotations [13], [14]. For example:

$$\|moon\| = \{e_{phobos}, e_{deimos}, \dots\}$$

All other denotations are modified accordingly. For example:

$$\begin{aligned} \|phobos\| &= \lambda s e_{phobos} \in s \quad (\text{where } \in \text{ is the set} \\ & \quad \text{membership operator}) \\ \|every\| &= \lambda s \lambda t (s \subseteq t) \quad (\text{where } s \subseteq t \text{ returns } True \\ & \quad \text{if } s \text{ is a subset of } t) \\ \|spins\| &= \text{the set of entities that spin} \end{aligned}$$

Thus the phrase "every moon spins" is interpreted as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \|every moon spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & (\lambda s \lambda t (s \subseteq t)) \|moon\| \|spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & \|moon\| \subseteq \|spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & True \quad (\text{because all moons in the universe of} \\ & \quad \text{discourse are in the set of things that spin}) \end{aligned}$$

The phrase "phobos spins" is interpreted as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \|phobos spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & (\lambda s e_{phobos} \in s) \|spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & e_{phobos} \in \|spins\| \\ \Rightarrow & True \quad (\text{because Phobos, in the universe of} \\ & \quad \text{discourse, is in the set of entities that spin}) \end{aligned}$$

B. An Event-Based Version of Montague Semantics

An event-based version of MS is needed to accommodate queries executed with respect to event-based reified triplestores [15]. Such a semantics has been developed and is described in earlier papers [15], [16] and in Peelar's Master's thesis [17].

It should be noted that binary relations can be obtained from event-based triplestores by first retrieving all triples of the type associated with the transitive verb, then extracting all event identifiers from those triples, followed by retrieving all subjects and objects associated with those events. The binary relation is obtained by pairing each subject with each object with which it is associated through an event.

In the event-based approach, rather than returning sets of entities as results of evaluating denotational expressions, sets of pairs are returned. Each pair (ent, evs) consists of an entity ent paired with a set of events evs which justify the entity being in the answer. For example:

$$\|phobos spins\| \Rightarrow \{(e_{phobos}, \{ev_{1360}\})\}$$

where ev_{1360} is the event identifier for the event in which e_{phobos} became a member of the set of entities which spin.

V. DENOTATIONS OF TRANSITIVE VERBS

The main contribution of this paper and the associated demo program beyond the results described in [16]-[18] is that Montague's treatment of transitive verbs is extended by using the $(n^2 - n)$ functions that are defined by the n -ary relation associated with each of the more complex transitive verbs. First Montague's treatment of transitive verbs will be introduced.

A. Montague's Treatment of Transitive Verbs

Transitive verbs in MS are handled using syntactic manipulation rather than with an explicit semantic denotation (see page 216 of [1]).

B. An Alternative Treatment of Transitive Verbs I

In earlier work [19], an explicit denotation for transitive verbs was developed that gives the same result as MS for some queries when their translations to lambda expressions are rewritten to their canonical forms. In this work, the denotation for “discover” was:

$$\|discover\| = \lambda z z(\lambda x \lambda y \text{ discover_pred}(y, x))$$

Enabling the denotation of “hall discovered phobos” to be translated as follows:

$$\begin{aligned} & \|hall\ discovered\ phobos\| \\ \Rightarrow & \|hall\| (\|discover\| \|phobos\|) \quad (\text{from parsing}) \\ \Rightarrow & \|hall\| ((\lambda z z (\lambda x \lambda y \text{ discover_pred}(y, x))) \\ & (\lambda f f e_{phobos})) \\ \Rightarrow & \|hall\| ((\lambda f f e_{phobos}) (\lambda x \lambda y \text{ discover_pred}(y, x))) \\ \Rightarrow & \|hall\| ((\lambda x \lambda y \text{ discover_pred}(y, x)) e_{phobos}) \\ \Rightarrow & \|hall\| (\lambda y \text{ discover_pred}(y, e_{phobos})) \\ \Rightarrow & (\lambda f f e_{hall}) (\lambda y \text{ discover_pred}(y, e_{phobos})) \\ \Rightarrow & (\lambda y \text{ discover_pred}(y, e_{phobos})) e_{hall} \\ \Rightarrow & \text{discover_pred}(e_{hall}, e_{phobos}) \\ \Rightarrow & \text{True} \quad (\text{because Hall discovered Phobos according} \\ & \text{to the universe of discourse}) \end{aligned}$$

However, this approach does not work for queries such as “hall discovered a moon”, since the denotation of the term-phrase “a moon” is more complex than the denotation of the term-phrase “phobos”.

C. An Alternative Treatment of Transitive Verbs II

One solution to the problem above is to use sets rather than characteristic functions (predicates) of those sets (as discussed in Section IV-A) in the denotations of transitive verbs. The basic idea [13] which is adopted in this paper is to consider transitive verbs as relations from the subjects or objects of those verbs to the events they participate in. Specifically, transitive verbs are denoted using the *function defined by the binary relation* (FDBR) [17] induced by the relation *rel* that underlies the verb:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FDBR}(rel) &= \{(x, image_x) \mid (\exists e) (x, e) \in rel \\ &\ \& \ image_x = \{y \mid (x, y) \in rel\}\} \end{aligned}$$

Briefly, $\text{FDBR}(rel)$ converts *rel* into a function without any loss of information by grouping together elements in the codomain that are related under the same element in the domain. For example, consider the relation underlying the active voice of “discover”, *discover_rel*:

$$\text{FDBR}(discover_rel) = \{(e_{hall}, \{ev_{1045}, ev_{1046}\}), \text{etc.}\dots\}$$

If the transitive verb is followed by a term-phrase such as “phobos” or “a moon”, then the function denoted by that term-phrase is used to “filter” the denotation of the transitive verb for relevant actors. For example:

$$\|discovered\| \|phobos\| \Rightarrow \{(e_{hall}, \{ev_{1045}\})\}$$

Similarly,

$$\|discovered\| \|a\ moon\| \Rightarrow \{(e_{hall}, \{ev_{1045}, ev_{1046}\}), \dots\}$$

The denotation of the transitive verb “discover” follows from the above:

$$\begin{aligned} \text{FDBR}(rel) &= \{(x, image_x) \mid \\ & (\exists e) (x, e) \in rel \ \& \ image_x = \{y \mid (x, y) \in rel\}\} \end{aligned}$$

where $\text{obj_fdbr}(evs)$ is the FDBR from the objects in the events of the set *evs* to the events they participate in within *evs*. In the examples above,

$$\begin{aligned} \text{obj_fdbr}(\{ev_{1045}, ev_{1046}\}) \\ = \{(e_{phobos}, \{ev_{1045}\}), (e_{deimos}, \{ev_{1046}\})\} \end{aligned}$$

When $\|phobos\|$ is applied to $\text{obj_fdbr}(\{ev_{1045}, ev_{1046}\})$, it filters the FDBR to only contain *relevant* pairs¹. If the FDBR is empty after filtering, then the pair corresponding to that FDBR is discarded. The function *gather(fdbr)* returns the set of all events in the second column of *fdbr*:

$$\text{gather}(fdbr) = \{ev \mid (\exists e)(\exists evs) (e, evs) \in fdbr \ \& \ ev \in evs\}$$

As another example, consider $\|discover\ every\ moon\|$:

$$\begin{aligned} & \|discover\ every\ moon\| \\ \Rightarrow & \|discover\| (\|every\ moon\|) \\ \Rightarrow & (\lambda t \{(s, relevs) \mid (s, evs) \in \text{FDBR}(discover_rel) \\ & \ \& \ t \text{ obj_fdbr}(evs) \neq \emptyset \\ & \ \& \ relevs = \text{gather}(\text{obj_fdbr}(evs))\}) \\ & (\|every\ moon\|) \\ \Rightarrow & \{(s, relevs) \mid (s, evs) \in \text{FDBR}(discover_rel) \\ & \ \& \ \|every\ moon\| \text{ obj_fdbr}(evs) \neq \emptyset \\ & \ \& \ relevs = \text{gather}(\text{obj_fdbr}(evs))\}) \\ \Rightarrow & \emptyset \quad (\text{owing to the fact that no entity in the} \\ & \text{universe of discourse discovered every moon}) \end{aligned}$$

Specifically, observe how the pair $(e_{hall}, \{ev_{1045}, ev_{1046}\}) \in \text{FDBR}(discover_rel)$ is treated above:

$$\begin{aligned} & \|every\ moon\| \text{ obj_fdbr}(\{ev_{1045}, ev_{1046}\}) \\ \Rightarrow & \|every\ moon\| \\ & \{(e_{phobos}, \{ev_{1045}\}), (e_{deimos}, \{ev_{1046}\})\} \\ \Rightarrow & \emptyset \quad (\text{owing to the fact that there exist entities} \\ & \text{other than } phobos \text{ and } deimos \text{ in the set } moon) \end{aligned}$$

In the event-based approach, the result of a verb-phrase such as “discovered phobos” is a list of pairs, each pair consisting of an entity which discovered phobos, paired with the set of events of type *discover* in which that entity was the subject and *e_{phobos}* was the object. In other words, the set of events in each pair can be thought of as a form of justification for the subject entity in the first field of that pair belonging in the result.

¹The notion of event relevance is discussed in more detail in [17]

D. Accommodating Chained Prepositional Phrases

The above approach can be extended to support prepositional phrases in queries with only minor changes [17], [20]. Briefly, the denotations of the prepositions act as filters to the denotation of the transitive verb they apply to. Consider, for example, the query “discovered in 1877 with a telescope”. In this query, the prepositions are “in 1877” and “with a telescope”. Performing this filtering is identical to the term-phrase filtering shown above, with some added logic to select columns other than the subject and object from the relation.

The denotation for a preposition applied to a term-phrase is a pair $(props, tmph)$ where $props$ is a set of properties that an FDBR should be constructed from (for example “implement”, “year”, or “location”), and $tmph$ is the term-phrase that will be applied to that resulting FDBR.

$$\begin{aligned} \|at\| &= \lambda t (\{location\}, t) \\ \|in\| &= \lambda t (\{location, year\}, t) \\ \|with\| &= \lambda t (\{implement\}, t) \\ \|using\| &= \lambda t (\{implement\}, t) \\ \|to\| &= \lambda t (\{subject\}, t) \end{aligned}$$

Under this approach, a prepositional phrase is treated in the same way as the term-phrase following the verb [17]. This approach is powerful enough that the word “by”, as in “discovered by”, can be treated in the same way as a preposition, enabling active and passive voices of transitive verbs to be treated in a uniform way. This was one of the key contributions to the semantics in Peelar’s Master’s thesis [17].

$$\|by\| = \lambda t (\{subject\}, t)$$

The denotation of the transitive verb is filtered in the order that the prepositions appear. To achieve this, the previous denotation for “discover” is modified such that $obj_fdbr(evs)$ is replaced with the more general $prop_fdbr(prop, evs)$, and the filtered FDBR from each applied termphrase is fed into the next preposition. If the passive form of the transitive verb is used, then the relation is flipped and the same logic applies.

E. Formal Denotations of Transitive Verbs

While a denotation for transitive verbs that allows for chained prepositional phrases and a unified treatment of active and passive voices improves expressibility, there are still a number of queries with transitive verbs that are not possible with the above approach. For example, consider the transitive verb “used”, as in the query “refractor_telescope_1 was used to discover phobos”. Here, the subject of the query is a refractor telescope, however it is neither the subject nor object of the relation underlying the denotation of “used”, which here is the same relation underlying the denotation of “discover” – it is an implement in that relation. A relation would need to be constructed from the “implement” property of the relation rather than the “subject” or “object” property as in the denotations in Section V-C in order to compute this.

This can be addressed with minor modifications to those denotations. Namely, the underlying relation is generalized to be n -ary. The columns of the n -ary relation are the properties of the event type of the transitive verb, with one column corresponding to the event identifier itself as in the denotation in Section V-C. A new function $make_binrel$ is introduced which converts an n -ary relation r into a binary relation by selecting two columns c_1 and c_2 from it:

$$make_binrel(r, c_1, c_2) = \dots$$

The FDBR is constructed from the underlying relation by using a new function that works on n -ary relations:

$$FDBR_{prop}(r) = FDBR(make_binrel(r, prop, eventid))$$

Here, $eventid$ refers to the column of the relation that contains the event. The denotation for transitive verbs is augmented with the property $prop$ used to form the binary relation from the n -ary relation, for example “subject”, “object”, or “implement”, replacing $FDBR(r)$ with $FDBR_{prop}(r)$. With these revisions, it is possible to express a denotation for the passive voice of the verb “used” (as in “what was used by hall”):

$$\begin{aligned} \|used\ by\| &= \\ \lambda t \{ (s, relex) \mid (s, evs) \in FDBR_{implement}(discover_rel) \\ &\ \& (t \ prop_fdbr(subject, evs) \neq \emptyset) \\ &\ \& relex = gather(obj_fdbr(evs)) \} \end{aligned}$$

Now, denotations for transitive verbs can be provided from any property to any other property, for example from implements to years, or from years to objects. This could be useful for constructing NL interfaces for other languages, such as French.

VI. THE $n^2 - n$ FUNCTIONS DEFINED BY AN n -ARY RELATION

The major contribution of this paper is to use the approach described above to considerably broaden the coverage of English compared to other systems and earlier [15]-[17] query interfaces developed in this direct line of research. First, notice that the phrase “discover x” often appears in contexts where the result expected is the set of subjects who discovered “x”. However, the words “discover”, “discovered” and “discovery” also appear in other contexts. For example, “discover with a telescope” (subjects expected), “discovered by hall” (objects expected), “how was x discovered” (implements expected), “who used a telescope to discover something in 1877” (subjects expected), “when was a telescope used to discover” (dates expected), “did hall use every telescope to discover phobos” (subjects expected).

It has been observed that different functions can be defined for a set of events. Suppose that the event is thought of as a row in an n -ary relation, for example consider the 5-ary discover relation [Table I].

The example in Section V-A used the function defined by the binary relation from subjects to objects. However, there are $n^2 - n$ ($25 - 5$) functions that can be defined from

TABLE I
 THE "DISCOVER" RELATION

subject	object	date	implement	location
...
hall	phobos	1877	refractor_telescope_1	us_naval_observatory
...

the 5-ary relation above if the function from a column to itself is excluded: subject to object, object to subject, subject to date, date to subject, date to subject, date to object etc. These functions can be used to answer any query about the discover relation, including those containing chained complex prepositional phrases.

VII. APPLICABILITY TO RELATIONAL DATABASES AND EVENT-BASED TRIPLESTORES

The semantics presented above lends itself to direct implementation with respect to relational databases in addition to event-based triplestores. Indeed, an event-based triplestore can be thought of as a set of tables in a relational database where each event corresponds to a row in a table. The event identifier, which is unique, becomes the row index. It is therefore possible to implement this approach on any relational database platform. Since this approach does not directly translate NL queries to a formal query language, it is amenable to implementation on any variant of SQL with no changes to the semantics. This applies to Semantic Web triplestores and their query interfaces as well. Note that the only SQL or SPARQL commands that the query interpreter issues are basic retrieval requests to obtain sets of tuples matching a simple pattern.

VIII. IMPLEMENTATION

Montague-type semantics are ideally suited for implementation as syntax-directed interpreters. One form of syntax-directed interpreter is an EAG in which the executable code of the interpreter has a close similarity to textbook attribute grammar notation, i.e. each production rule in the grammar is closely associated with a semantic rule defining how the meaning of the language construct, whose syntax is defined by the production rule, is obtained from the meaning of its syntactic components. This can be achieved in a higher-order functional programming language by the use of higher-order functions called "parser combinators" which correspond to "orelse" and "then" in a context-free grammar. Accordingly, the Solarman NLQI is built as an executable specification of an attribute grammar using the X-SAIGA parser combinator library [21], [18] that was designed and implemented in Haskell as part of an earlier project.

The Haskell code, which is approximately 2,800 lines long, can be found at [22].

Note that syntactic ambiguity is accommodated by having the parser generate more than one syntax tree, each of which determines an order of application of the functions that are denoted by the words and phrases in the query.

The X-SAIGA parser combinator library is available on the Haskell "Hackage" package archive [23].

IX. FUTURE WORK

At this time, this approach requires an event-based triplestore or relational database in order to handle chained prepositional phrases. There is a clear need for effective NLQIs to non-event-based Semantic Web triplestores. It may be possible to build a translator from conventional triplestores to event-based triplestores using Semantic Web OWL schemas, or, in the absence of those, machine learning approaches. This approach also currently is only viable for databases with tens of thousands of facts, whereas Semantic Web triplestores such as DBpedia [24] can represent millions of facts. Research is ongoing towards scaling up this approach to address these needs.

X. CONCLUSION

The approach described in this paper extends previous work on building natural-language query interfaces to online data stores by providing an explicit Montague-style efficient denotation for transitive verbs; and an approach for accommodating queries containing chained complex prepositional phrases. The viability of this approach was demonstrated by building an NL query interface to an event-based semantic-web triplestore containing thousands of facts. The approach could be used with relational databases by considering the n^2n functions defined by each n -ary relation associated with n -ary transitive verbs. Research on scaling and speeding up this approach is ongoing, with the goal being to create an interface to query data stores containing millions of facts.

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